

understand how exactly the addition of the same quantity of the same electrolyte to the same acids having the same groups but different orientation should produce different effects. The authors think that it may probably be due to the formation of molecular complexes or some chemical interaction between acids and the electrolytes. Further experiments on viscosity, conductivity and absorption spectra are in progress in this laboratory.

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Investigations on the Acid Nature of some Derivatives of Sulphur, Selenium and Tellurium.

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Four principal methods were used by Hantzsch in supporting his extended theory of pseudo-acids. They have already been referred to in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1925, 1, 247) and it has been shown that, according to the new theory, it was the "ionogen" bond between the "acid" hydrogen atom and the acid radical which was responsible for the acid properties and not the concentration of the hydrogen ion, as was supposed

in the classical electrolytic dissociation theory. The above methods (the comparison of the absorption spectra of the acid, its salts and esters in different solvents, the velocity of reaction of the acid with diazoacetic ester, the velocity of inversion of cane sugar in concentrated solutions and the action on indicators in different solvents) were then used to investigate acid properties of some derivatives of sulphur, selenium and tellurium, and conclusions drawn as to their comparative strength.

1. Methyl- and Ethyl-sulphuric Acids, $RHSO_4$.

In pure condition these acids react very energetically with diazoacetic ester. Even very dilute aqueous solutions are active towards the indicator, and must therefore be classified as true acids corresponding to the formula, $[RO \cdot SO_3] \cdot H$. (In all these experiments dimethyl-amino-azobenzene was used as indicator). These acids, however, react as pseudo-acids in dilute alcoholic solutions, and even the concentrated ethereal solutions are neutral to the indicator. It must, therefore, be the pseudo-acid $RO \cdot SO_3 \cdot OH$ which is present under these conditions.

2. Selenious Acid, H_2SeO_3 .

The conductivity of aqueous solutions of selenious acid has already been determined by Ostwald (Landolt-Börnstein, *Tabellen*, 1112). He came to the conclusion that this acid was one of the weak acids, for, even in a dilution of 1024 litres the conductivity was only about 60% of that of a monobasic acid. He therefore came to the conclusion that this acid was practically a monobasic acid of the formula $(HO \cdot SeO) \cdot H$.

This acid was investigated according to all the four methods. The solid acid, provided it is absolutely dry, does not react with diazoacetic ester. The solution of the indicator in a solvent, which does not dissolve the acid,

is not colored red by the crystals of the acid. All these experiments lead us to the conclusion that the acid is a pseudo-acid of the formula $[(HO)_2 Se.O]_x$.

Table I gives the absorption spectrum of the acid in different solvents. Curve 1 corresponds to the absorption of a 0.2*N* solution in aqueous alcohol, curve 2 to that of a similar solution in water, and also in 20% sulphuric acid (where the selenious acid is practically fully undissociated) and curve 3 to that of a solution of the acid in an excess of sodium hydroxide. The undissociated acid, the partially dissociated acid and the sodium salt show similar absorption. The alcoholic solution (which, according to the indicator experiments given below, contains only the pseudo-acid) has a slightly stronger absorption, and the order of succession of the curves is thus very similar to that of acetic acid (Hantzsch). We must, therefore, draw the conclusion that the molecules of the acid have been more or less saturated owing to the grouping of water molecules round them and have consequently a weaker absorption.

Table II gives the velocities of inversion of cane sugar by selenious acid in aqueous solutions. x Represents the amount of sugar inverted at the time t and b , the amount of sugar originally present in the solution. The constant k was then calculated according to the formula for monomolecular reactions :

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{b}{b-x}$$

The equivalent activity (according to Ostwald, *J. pr. Chem.*, 29, 385) which is represented by k/N rises with increasing dilution, and indicates the increase in the concentration of the true acid in dilute solutions. The velocity of inversion k naturally decreases with increasing dilution. Table III gives a comparison of the values for

TABLE I.

Absorption Spectra of Selenious Acid.

formic, acetic (A. Weissberger, *Dissertation*, Leipzig), and selenious acids. The order of magnitude of all the three acids is the same, and this is perhaps one more proof for the monobasic nature of selenious acid.

The velocities of reaction with diazoacetic ester are given in Table IV. The velocity is very small, and could not be determined in very concentrated solutions owing to the limited solubility of the acid in water. The aqueous solution can be completely neutralized in its action on diazoacetic ester by the addition of only one mol of alkali, and this proves that the true selenious acid present in the aqueous solutions is in the form of the hydrate of the monobasic acid :

and not as

The greater part of the acid is, however, present as the pseudo-acid,

or its hydrate.

With the addition of about 10 mols of alcohol the acid becomes completely inactive towards diazoacetic ester, and must therefore be present as the pseudo-acid in this concentration. The same solution is also neutral to indicators. The addition of a few drops of water produces however a sufficient amount of the true acid to give a red coloration.

The general conclusion to be drawn from all these experiments is that selenious acid is an associated pseudo-acid in the pure condition. The aqueous solutions contain a very large proportion of the pseudo-acid and only very small percentage of the hydrate of the true acid.

Even relatively concentrated solutions of the acid in alcohol contain only the pseudo-acid.

3. Selenic acid, H_2SeO_4 .

It was not possible to obtain the perfectly dry acid. The acid used in the experiments was 98%. It is known to be a strong acid, comparable in strength to sulphuric acid. It dissolves in water under considerable evolution of heat and forms the true hydroxonium salt $HO.SeO_3.H_2O$. This aqueous solution therefore reacts very vigorously with diazoacetic ester, the reaction in a 0.3 *N* solution being very nearly explosive. A small amount of methyl alcohol was therefore added to this solution in order to transform some of the true acid into the pseudo-acid and thus reduce the velocity of the reaction a little. The reaction velocities are given in Table V. The values for sulphuric acid are also given for comparison.

The velocity increases more rapidly than the concentration, thus showing that the undissociated molecules of selenic acid are more active than the ions. The pure acid is therefore to be considered as the true acid, $[SeO_4H].H$ and the true oxonium salt as $[SeO_4H].H_2O$. This oxonium salt, as salt of a very strong acid and an exceedingly weak base (water), possesses "very nearly" but not exactly the same strength as the free acid. With increasing dilution, the amount of this salt increases and the velocity of the reaction decreases.

Like sulphuric acid (Hantzsch, *loc. cit.*) selenic acid exists as the true ethyl-oxonium salt even in the most dilute alcoholic solutions, and reacts energetically with diazoacetic ester, and also gives a coloration with the indicator. In other words, it dissolves in alcohol with the formation of the salt, $[HSeO_4]. [H_2O(C_2H_5)]$. Unlike sulphuric acid it does not dissolve appreciably in ether.

4. Sulphinic and Seleninic Acids, RSO_2H and $RSeO_2H$.

These acids are very difficult to obtain in the pure condition. It is well-known that the sulphonic acids are stronger than sulphuric acid. The reason of this is that the proportion of O : H is greater in the case of the former than in the case of the latter (3 : 1 as compared to 4 : 2). The "acid" hydrogen atom of the sulphonic acids can therefore be in loose connection with 3 oxygen atoms instead of with only 2 in the case of sulphuric acid. The sulphonic acids also fulfil the expectation that they would be stronger than sulphurous acid (O : H = 2 : 1 and 3 : 2).

(a) Benzenesulphinic Acid, $C_6H_5.SO_2H$.

This acid is very unstable when exposed to the air. It decomposes diazoacetic ester only very slowly and the solid acid is therefore the pseudo-acid of the formula

In aqueous solutions the acid is present as the true acid, $C_6H_5 \cdot SO_2 \cdot H$, as the solutions are active against both diazoacetic ester and the indicator. In about 50 mols. of alcohol it is completely transformed into the pseudo-acid, and ether inactivates it even in more concentrated solutions. In both cases we have the alcoholate or the etherate of the pseudo-acid,

in solution.

(b) Ethylsulphinic Acid, $C_2H_5.SO_2H$.

This acid is a little weaker than the above, but still considerably stronger than sulphurous acid. 12.5 mols. of alcohol and 4.5 mols. of ether are necessary to make the acid completely inactive towards diazoacetic ester and the

indicator. In these solutions, it is present as the pseudo-acid,

Both these acids are very unstable and have to be used up very soon after the preparation.

(c) Ethylseleninic Acid, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{SeO}_2\text{H}$.

This acid could not be investigated in the pure condition, as it is even more unstable than the two acids mentioned above. The aqueous solution, prepared by addition of the calculated quantity of a strong acid to its salt, does not decompose diazoacetic ester. The change of color in the indicator caused by this solution is practically negligible and is completely destroyed by the addition of a couple of drops of alcohol. This acid is therefore present as the pseudo-acid,

even in aqueous solutions.

5. Telluric Acid, H_2TeO_6 .

This acid is very weak and at the same time very sparingly soluble in water. It does not react with either diazoacetic ester or with the indicator. It is thus a pseudo-acid of the formula,

The salts of this acid can even be titrated by means of a strong acid just like carbonates or cyanides.

6. Telluric Acids.

It is known that telluric acid exists in three different modifications (Mylius, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2205). The ordinary acid is a dihydrate $\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and is a very weak acid. The existence of a methyl ether of the formula $\text{Te}(\text{OCH}_3)_6$ indicates, however, that this acid could perhaps be better represented by the formula

Te(OH)₆. This acid when heated in a sealed tube to 140° is transformed into the so-called *allotelluric acid* which is obtained in the form of a sticky viscous mass and is a comparatively strong acid. The ordinary telluric acid possesses a normal molecular weight in water, while *allotelluric acid* has a molecular weight corresponding to a formula between (H₆TeO₆)₃ and (H₆TeO₆)₄. By heating both these acids in an open tube the pure acid, H₆TeO₄ is obtained. The latter is insoluble in water and does not give an acid reaction.

All the three acids were investigated as regards their reactivity towards diazoacetic ester and the indicator. Ordinary telluric acid, which has a conductivity of the same order of magnitude as hydrocyanic acid, is inactive towards both these reagents and hence possesses the formula Te(OH)₆. The potassium salt, obtained by precipitation with strong caustic potash, is very nearly completely dissociated in aqueous solutions, and the solution can be titrated against strong acids just like the corresponding carbonate or cyanide.

Allotelluric acid is a fairly strong acid and its aqueous solution has a high conductivity. It reacts vigorously with diazoacetic ester and the indicator. It can however be completely inactivated by the addition of about 4 to 5 mols. of alcohol (calculated on 1 atom of Te). *Allotelluric acid* must therefore be regarded as a true acid. Its behaviour and also its formation from the dihydrate can be best explained by means of the formula,

The pure acid is neutral towards both the above reagents and must be represented by the formula,

Hantzsch has already shown that the strength of an acid depends, in addition to the negative nature of the acid radical, on the ratio of the oxygen atoms of the acid radical to the acid hydrogen atoms. Sulphuric and selenic acids are thus strong acids and the latter is only slightly weaker owing to the less negative nature of its acid radical. It is also more easily transformed into the pseudo-acid. Ordinary telluric acid H_6TeO_6 has the ratio $O : H = 6 : 6$, and is naturally much weaker than both these acids. With increasing ratio of $O : H$ the possibility of a hydrogen atom forming a hydroxyl group, characteristic of a pseudo-acid, naturally increases.

TABLE II.

*Velocity of Inversion of Cane Sugar with
Selenious Acid at 25.°*

10 % Sugar + 2N H_2SeO_3				10 % Sugar + 0.5N H_2SeO_3			
Time (min)	x	$\frac{\log b - \log (b-x)}$	k	Time (min)	x	$\frac{\log b - \log (b-x)}$	k
0	0.0		..	0	0.0	...	...
50	1.5	0891	0.000088	1365	2.51	0687	0.000050
65	1.78	0453	0.000080	2880	6.16	1931	0.000067
245	2.6	0701	0.000088	4560	8.87	3161	0.000068
1315	4.1	1163	0.000088	5700	10.15	3893	0.000069
1700	5.3	1574	0.000092	∞	17.45	...	...
2090	9.35	3225	0.000083				
∞	17.45	...	...				
Mean value for $k = 0.000086$				Mean value for $k = 0.000068$			

$$\text{Equivalent activity} = \frac{k}{N} = \frac{0.000086}{2} = 0.000043 \text{ in } 2N \text{ solution}$$

$$\text{and } \text{''} = \frac{0.000068}{0.5} = 0.000136 \text{ in } 0.5N \text{ solution.}$$

TABLE III.

Velocities of Inversion of Cane Sugar with Formic, Acetic and Selenious Acids.

Normality	Formic Acid.		Acetic Acid.		Selenious Acid.	
	k	$\frac{k}{N}$	k	$\frac{k}{N}$	k	$\frac{k}{N}$
4	0.000192	0.000048	0.000087	0.000009	—	—
2	0.0000978	0.0000489	—	—	0.000086	0.000043
1	0.000058	0.000058	—	—	—	—
0.5	0.0000332	0.0000664	0.00001	0.00002	0.000083	0.00026

TABLE IV.

Velocity of Reaction of Selenious Acid with Diazoacetic Ester.

Vol. of N_2 measured	0.01N	0.1N.
1/8 *	(0.00221)	(0.0294)
2/8	0.00284	0.0411
3/8	0.00301	0.048
4/8	0.00334	0.0516
5/8	0.00324	0.0533
6/8	—	0.0517
7/8	—	0.0444

* As exactly 1/1000 mols. of the acid and of diazoacetic ester were used, complete decomposition would have produced 22.4 cms. of N_2 measured at N. T. P. This volume, therefore, represented 3/8 of the reaction. The numbers in the first vertical column denote how much of the diazoacetic ester has been decomposed and the next two columns give the corresponding velocity constant at that time.

The bracketed values cannot be taken as certain, due to the disturbing influences at the beginning.

TABLE V.

Velocities of Reaction of Selenic and Sulphuric Acids with Diazoacetic Ester.

	Vol. of N ₂ measured, 8/8=22.4 c.c.	0.005N in water.	0.01 N in water.	0.1N in water.	0.2 N in water.	0.3 N in 15% CH ₃ OH.	0.3 N in 30% CH ₃ OH.
Selenic Acid.	1/8	(0.0046)	(0.0089)	(0.134)	(0.206)	(0.74)	0.835
	2/8	0.0060	0.0106	0.196	0.490	1.15	0.870
	3/8	0.00625	0.0112	0.228	0.587	1.23	0.870
	4/8	0.00613	0.0106	0.240	0.675	1.19	0.867
	5/8	0.00540	0.0090	0.248	0.730	1.25	0.891
	6/8	—	—	0.210	0.645	1.17	0.815
	7/8	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sulphuric Acid.	1/8	0.00476	0.0081	(0.157)	(0.371)	0.955	1.08
	2/8	0.00592	0.00975	0.206	0.542	1.108	0.99
	3/8	0.00670	0.0099	0.248	0.711	1.175	1.04
	4/8	0.00647	0.0091	0.266	0.815	1.153	1.02
	5/8	—	0.0105	0.260	0.880	1.152	1.04
	6/8	—	—	0.217	0.768	1.110	0.987
	7/8	—	—	—	—	—	—

EXPERIMENTAL.

1. Selenious Acid.—Powdered metallic selenium was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid by warming and the solution heated to dryness. The residue was taken up with very little water and the acid purified by recrystallisation.

0.1292 g. selenious acid mixed with one drop of the indicator solution gave no coloration when 0.58 c.c. or 0.464 g. alcohol were added to it. In mols, this is equivalent to 10.1.

The velocity of inversion was measured by the usual method. The sugar solution was exactly 20% before being mixed with the acid solutions, which were 4*N* and 1*N* respectively. The strength of both the sugar and the acid were reduced to 10% and 2*N* and 0.5*N* respectively after mixing. The polarimeter tube was surrounded by a water-jacket through which a constant stream of water at 25° was kept running.

The velocity of the reaction with diazoacetic ester was measured according to the method described by Schreiter and Weissberger (*Dissertation*, Leipzig, 1924; see also this *Journal*, 1925, 1, 247). 0.1140 g. of the ester (0.001 mol) were always used. The vessels used in these experiments were carefully cleaned and in each case a few grains of pure sand, which had been previously boiled with acid and distilled water, were added in order to facilitate the evolution of the gas. The diazoacetic ester was first measured off by means of a calibrated pipette, a small known amount of water added and finally a slightly more concentrated solution of the acid than was required, thus producing the required concentration in the reaction mixture. The time and the volume of the nitrogen collected were then read off, the latter reduced to N.T.P. and the values for the coefficient were calculated according to the usual formula. The amount of diazoacetic ester taken would evolve 22.4 c.c. nitrogen after complete decomposition. The coefficients given in the Table in the theoretical part for $\frac{1}{3}$, $\frac{2}{3}$, etc., mean that the coefficient has been calculated for that particular time when the volume of nitrogen evolved was $22.4 \times \frac{1}{3}$, $22.4 \times \frac{2}{3}$, etc.

2. Selenic acid was prepared according to the method of Meyer and Moldenhauer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 116, 193). This consists of the oxidation of the selenious acid by means of chloric acid. The thick

syrup obtained in this way could not be completely dehydrated even after being kept for weeks in vacuum over P_2O_5 .

3. Methyl and ethyl sulphuric acids could not be prepared by Kremann's method (*Monatsh*, 1900, 31, 216) as this was both costly and troublesome. The method of Berthelot (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, [2], 19, 295) gave quite satisfactory yields. The only precaution, that is absolutely necessary, is the concentrating of the solution of barium ethyl sulphate in vacuum at a temperature not exceeding 55° .

4. Telluric acid was prepared in exactly the same manner as the corresponding selenium compound. The acid is insoluble in water but soluble in alkalis.

5. Telluric acid was prepared by the method of Mylius (*loc. cit.*), by the oxidation of the lower acid by means of chromic acid. Allotelluric acid was prepared by heating the ordinary acid for 3 hours in a sealed tube at 140° . It has a slightly yellow color when hot but is colorless when cold.

6. Benzenesulphonic Acid.—20 g. Benzenesulphonyl chloride were dissolved in water and 10 g. of zinc dust were added slowly under cooling. The mixture was cautiously poured into water and filtered. The insoluble part containing the zinc salt and the unused zinc dust was then suspended in water and soda solution added to it. The filtrate from this mixture contained the sodium salt which was purified by crystallisation, decomposed by means of the calculated quantity of hydrochloric acid and the acid thus obtained was washed and dried. White needles, m. p. $83-84^\circ$. For inactivation against the indicator, 0.284 g. required 6.2 c.c. or 4.96 g. alcohol. This corresponds to 53.5 mols.

7. Ethylsulphonic acid was prepared by means of Grignard's reaction. 20 g. of ethyl bromide were

dissolved in 50 c.c. of dry ether and 4.2 g. magnesium ribbon were added in small pieces. After the reaction was finished a stream of dry SO_2 was passed into it and the flask strongly cooled. The white precipitate of the magnesium salt was thoroughly washed and dried. It crystallises with 2 molecules of water. The salt was then decomposed by the calculated amount of dilute sulphuric acid. It is obtained in the form of a colorless syrup and decomposes slowly at the ordinary temperature. 2.1 g. Mg salt + 0.98 g. sulphuric acid (calculated amount) + 1 drop of the indicator required 14.4 c.c. or 11.52 g. alcohol and 9.25 c.c. or 6.66 g. ether for complete inactivation. This corresponds to 12.5 and 4.3 mols. respectively.

8. Ethylseleninic acid was prepared in exactly the same manner as above, using selenium dioxide instead of sulphur dioxide. This acid has practically no acidic properties and even forms a compound with hydrochloric acid having the formula $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{SeO.OH.HCl}$ (Rathke, *Ann. Chem.*, 1869, 152, 216).

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